

Condensation of Pimelyl Chloride and Suberyl Chloride with Di- and Polyhydric Phenols, their Methyl Ethers and Halogenated Derivatives

D. Chakravarti and (Mrs.) Minati Saha

Pimelyl chloride and suberyl chloride have been condensed with resorcinol, resorcinol monomethyl ether, resorcinol dimethyl ether, 4-chloro resorcinol, 4-chloro resorcinol dimethyl ether, veratrole, pyrogallol trimethyl ether, 4-bromo resorcinol, and 4-bromo resorcinol dimethyl ether in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride producing 1,7-diones and ω -(substituted benzoyl)-hexanoic acids and 1 : 8-diones and ω -(substituted benzoyl)-heptanoic acids respectively.

In earlier papers Chakravarti and coworkers¹⁻⁵ have reported the condensation of various monohydric phenols and their ethers with succinyl chloride, glutaryl chloride, adipyl chloride, pimelyl chloride, suberyl chloride, azeloyl chloride and sebasoyl chloride.

In the present communication the authors have described the condensation of pimelyl chloride and suberyl chloride with various di- and polyhydric phenols, their methyl ethers and halogenated derivatives in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride catalyst.

The condensation of the above dibasic acid dichlorides with the aforementioned di- and polyhydric phenols, their methyl ethers and halogenated derivatives, has been found to occur smoothly at 0-5° in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and nitrobenzene or tetrachloroethane as solvent leading to the formation of diaryl diketones (I) in good yield together with some aryl keto acids (II) in small quantity and this serves as an excellent method for the synthesis of aromatic 1 : 7 and 1 : 8 diketones.

(I)

(II)

where $n = 5$ or 6 .

In all these condensation reactions the acyl group is found to enter without any exception the position which has the maximum directive influence of the hydroxy or the alkoxy groups.

The constitution of the products is established by their oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate to the corresponding β -resorcylic acid derivatives.

1. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 607.
2. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 32.
3. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 463.
4. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 352.
5. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 744.

TABLE I

Condensation of Di and Polyhydric Phenols, their Ethers and Halogenated Derivatives with Pimetyl Chloride

Phenols and Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Required %		
1. Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene)	a) 1,7 bis-[2,4-dihydroxy phenyl]-heptane 1,7-dione, m.p. 165° (acetic acid); reported m.p. 166°. [Rybakova and Zilberman; <i>Zhur Obshchei Khim.</i> , 31 , 1272, (1961)].	$C_{15}H_{20}O_6$ [I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 5]	C; 65.98 H; 6.07	66.28 5.81	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 213°; (ethanol) [Found : N, 15.67; C ₃₁ H ₃₉ O ₁₂ N ₈ requires N, 15.91%].	Methylation gives a product identical with the diketone obtained from resorcinol dimethyl ether and pimetyl chloride. A violet colouration obtained with FeCl ₃ solution.
	b) ω-[2,4-dihydroxy benzoyl]-hexanoic acid, m.p. 126° (hot water)	$C_{13}H_{16}O_5$ [II, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 5]	C; 61.74 H; 6.13	61.90 6.35	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 146° (methanol) [Found : N, 13.38; C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₈ requires N, 12.96%].	
2. Resorcinol Mono-methyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,7-bis-[2-hydroxy,4-methoxy phenyl]-heptane 1,7-dione, m.p. 106° (ethanol)	$C_{21}H_{24}O_6$ [I, R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 5]	C; 68.09 H; 7.06	67.74 6.45	Dioxime, m.p. 162° (dil. ethanol) [Found : N, 6.60; C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₂ requires N, 6.96%]	Products develop a violet colouration with ferric chloride solution. Infrared spectrum of the diketone (CHCl ₃) ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹); 1639; 1600, 1525, 1480, 1030, 851, 812.
	b) ω-[2-hydroxy, 4-methoxy benzoyl]-hexanoic acid, m.p. 134° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ [II, R = OH; R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 5]	C; 62.93 H; 6.58	63.15 6.77	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 101° (ethanol) [Found : N, 12.20; C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₄ requires N, 12.56%]	
3. Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene)	1,7 bis-[2,4-dimethoxy phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione, m.p. 128° (ethanol).	$C_{23}H_{28}O_6$ [I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 5]	C; 68.83 H; 6.75	69.00 7.00	Dioxime, m.p. 164° (ethanol) [Found : N, 6.80; C ₂₃ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₂ requires N, 6.51%]	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ gives β-resorcylic acid dimethyl ether, m.p. 106°.

TABLE I—Contd

Phenols and Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Required %		
4. 4-Chloro Resorcinol (in nitro benzene)	a) 1,7 bis-[2,4-dihydroxy, 5-chlorophenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione, m.p. 203° (acetic acid)	$C_{19}H_{16}O_6Cl_2$	C, 55.04	55.21	Dioxime, m.p. 229° (dil. ethanol)	Methylation gives a product identical with the diketone obtained from 4-chloro resoreinol dimethyl ether and pimelyl chloride (mixed m.p. 162–163°).
		[I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 5]	H, 4.69	4.36	[Found : N, 6.15; C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂ Cl ₂ requires N, 6.32%]	
b)	ω-[2,4-dihydroxy, 5-chlorobenzoyl]-hexanoic acid, m.p. 147–148° (dil. ethanol).	$C_{19}H_{18}O_5Cl$	C, 54.63	54.45		
		[II, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 5]	H, 5.13	5.24		
5. 4-Chloro Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitro benzene).	a) 1,7 bis-(2,4-dimethoxy, 5-chlorophenyl)-heptane 1,7 dione, m.p. 163°.	$C_{23}H_{26}O_6Cl_2$	C, 58.72	58.85	Dioxime, m.p. 142° (dil. methanol)	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Infrared spectrum (KBr Wafer); νmax (cm ⁻¹); 2857, 1656, 1595, 1495, 1276, 1022, 835.
		[I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 5]	H, 5.34	5.54	[Found : N, 5.39; C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ requires N, 5.61%].	
b)	ω-[2,4-dimethoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl]-hexanoic acid, m.p. 127° (dil. ethanol).	$C_{15}H_{19}O_5Cl$	C, 57.15	57.23		No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
		[II, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 5]	H, 5.91	6.04		
6. Pyrogallol Trimethyl Ether (in nitro benzene).	a) 1,7 bis-[2-hydroxy, 3,4-dimethoxy phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione, m.p. 114° (ethanol) reported m.p. 116° [Kiichiro Kakemi <i>et al.</i> ; Yakugaku Zasshi, 86 , 778–86 (1966)].	$C_{23}H_{28}O_8$	C, 63.66	63.89	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 176° (methanol)	A violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
		[I, R = OH; R ₁ = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = H; n = 5]	H, 6.12	6.48	[Found : N, 14.32; C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₁₄ N ₆ ; requires N, 14.15%].	
b)	ω-[2-hydroxy, 3,4-dimethoxy benzoyl]-hexanoic acid, m.p. 151° (dil. ethanol).	$C_{15}H_{20}O_6$	C, 60.69	60.81	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 207° (ethanol)	Wine red colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
		[II, R = OH; R ₁ = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = H; n = 5]	H, 6.83	6.76	[Found : N, 11.32; C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₄ requires N, 11.77%].	

TABLE I—Contd.

Phenols and Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Required %		
7. Veratrole (in tetrachloro ethane).	a) 1,7 bis-[3,4-dimethoxy phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione, m.p. 95° (ethanol).	$C_{23}H_{28}O_6$ [I, $R_2=R_3=OMe$; $R=R_1=H$; $n=5$].	C, 68.85	69.00	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 188° (benzene) [Found : N, 14.41; $C_{35}H_{58}O_{12}N_6$ requires N, 14.73%].	No characteristic colouration with $FeCl_3$. Oxidation by alkaline $KMnO_4$ gives a product identical with veratric acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 181°.
			H, 6.84	7.00		
	b) ω -[3,4-dimethoxy benzoyl]-hexanoic acid, m.p. 99° (dil. ethanol).	$C_{15}H_{20}O_5$ [II, $R_2=R_3=OMe$; $R=R_1=H$; $n=5$].	C, 64.43	64.29		No characteristic colouration with $FeCl_3$.
			H, 7.33	7.14		
8. 4-Bromo Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,7 bis-[2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromo phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione, m.p. 186° (ethanol).	$C_{19}H_{18}O_6Br_2$ [I, $R=R_2=OH$; $R_1=H$; $R_3=Br$; $n=5$].	C, 45.20	45.41		Produces violet colouration with $FeCl_3$ solution. Methylation gives a product identical with the diketone obtained from 4-bromo resorcinol dimethyl ether and pimelyl chloride.
			H, 3.62	3.59		
	b) ω -[2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromobenzoyl]-hexanoic acid, m.p. 140° (hot water).	$C_{13}H_{15}O_6Br$ [II, $R=R_2=OH$; $R_1=H$; $R_3=Br$; $n=5$].	C, 46.81	47.12		Gives a wine red colouration with $FeCl_3$ solution.
			H, 4.38	4.53		
9. 4-Bromo Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether, (in nitrobenzene).	1,7 bis-[2,4-dimethoxy 5-bromo phenyl]-heptane 1,7 dione, m.p. 137° (ethanol).	$C_{23}H_{26}O_6Br_2$ [I, $R=R_2=OMe$; $R_1=H$; $R_3=Br$; $n=5$].	C, 49.04	49.46	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., (ethanol) m.p. 120° [Found : N, 12.03; $C_{35}H_{54}O_{12}N_6Br_2$ requires N, 12.20%].	Gives no characteristic colouration with $FeCl_3$ solution. Oxidation with alkaline $KMnO_4$ gives 5-bromo- β -resorcylic acid dimethyl ether, m.p. 194°.
			H, 4.82	4.66		

TABLE II
Condensation of Di- and Polyhydric Phenols, their Ethers and Halogenated Derivatives with Suberyl Chloride

Phenols and Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Required %		
1. Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,8 bis [2,4-dihydroxy phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione m.p. 189° (acetic acid).	$C_{20}H_{22}O_6$ [I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 6].	C, 67.24 H, 5.93	67.04 6.15	Dioxime, m.p. 228° (dil. ethanol); [Found : N, 6.92 $C_{20}H_{24}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.21%].	Produces violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Methylation gives a product identical with the diketone obtained from resorcinol dimethyl ether and suberyl chloride.
	b) ω-[2,4-dihydroxy benzoyl]-heptanoic acid m.p. 141° (hot water).	$C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ [II, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 6].	C, 63.05 H, 6.98	63.16 6.77	2 : 4 D.N.P.H. m.p. 129° (methanol) [Found : N, 12.90; $C_{20}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires N, 12.56%].	Infrared spectrum (KBr Wafer) ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹); 3356, 3226, 1634, 1600, 1517, 880.
2. Resorcinol Monomethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,8 bis-[2-hydroxy, 4-methoxy phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione m.p. 155° (acetic acid).	$C_{22}H_{26}O_6$ [I, R = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; R ₂ = OMe; n = 6].	C, 68.18 H, 7.00	68.39 6.74	Dioxime, m.p. 179° (dil. ethanol) [Found : N, 6.50; $C_{22}H_{28}O_6N_2$ requires N, 6.73%].	Violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
	b) ω-[2-hydroxy, 4-methoxy benzoyl]-heptanoic acid m.p. 135° (hot water).	$C_{15}H_{20}O_5$ [II, R = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; R ₂ = OMe; n = 6].	C, 64.06 H, 6.95	64.28 7.14		
3. Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,8 bis-[2,4-dimethoxy phenyl]-1,8 octane dione m.p. 140° (ethanol).	$C_{24}H_{30}O_6$ [I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 6].	C, 69.23 H, 7.63	69.56 7.25	Dioxime, m.p. 152° (dil ethanol) [Found : N, 6.66; $C_{25}H_{34}O_6N_2$ requires N, 6.11%].	No colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ solution gives 2,4-dimethoxy benzoic acid, m.p. 106°.
	b) ω-[2,4-dimethoxy benzoyl]-heptanoic acid m.p. 106° (hot water).	$C_{16}H_{22}O_5$ [II, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = R ₃ = H; n = 6].	C, 65.29 H, 7.30	65.31 7.48		Infrared spectrum (KBr Wafer) ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹); 2875, 1253, 1024, 1660, 1600, 1500, 841, 816. No colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Infrared spectrum (KBr Wafer) ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹); 2857, 1656, 1600, 1500, 1712, 1031, 838, 813.

TABLE II—Contd

Phenols and Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Required %		
4. 4-Chloro Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,8 bis-[2,4-dihydroxy, 5-chlorophenyl]-octane 1,8 dione m.p. 227° (acetic acid).	$C_{20}H_{20}O_8Cl_2$ [I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 6].	C, 56.43 H, 4.45	56.21 4.68	Dioxime, m.p. 214° [Found : N, 6.08 $C_{20}H_{22}O_8N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 6.13%].	Violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Methylation gives a product identical with the diketone obtained from 4-chlororesorcinol dimethyl ether and suberyl chloride, m.p. 186° (mixed m.p. 186°). Infrared spectrum (KBr Wafer) ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹); 3448, 1645, 1595, 1500, 895, 858.
	b) ω-[2,4-dihydroxy, 5-chloro benzoyl]-heptanoic acid, m.p. 141° (dil. methanol)	$C_{14}H_{17}O_5Cl$ [II, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 6].	C, 55.54 H, 6.01	55.91 5.66	2 : 4 D.N.P.H. m.p. 172° (methanol) [Found : N, 11.69; $C_{20}H_{22}N_2O_8Cl$ requires N, 11.66%].	
5. 4-Chloro Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,8 bis-[2,4-dimethoxy, 5-chloro phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione, m.p. 186° (acetic acid).	$C_{24}H_{28}O_8Cl_2$ [I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 6].	C, 59.37 H, 5.48	59.62 5.79	Dioxime, m.p. 191° (dil methanol) [Found : N, 5.21; $C_{24}H_{30}O_8N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 5.46%].	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
	b) ω-[2,4-dimethoxy, 5-chlorobenzoyl]-heptanoic acid, m.p. 106° (hot water).	$C_{16}H_{21}O_5Cl$ [II, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₁ = H; R ₃ = Cl; n = 6].	C, 58.73 H, 6.55	58.45 6.39	2 : 4 D.N.P.H. m.p. 188° (methanol) [Found : N, 10.86; $C_{22}H_{25}O_8N_2Cl$ requires N, 11.01%].	
6. Pyrogallol Trimethyl Ether (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,8 bis-[2-hydroxy, 3,4-dimethoxy phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione, m.p. 160° (acetic acid). reported m.p. 163°; [Kichiro Kakemi <i>et al.</i> Yakugaku Zasshi 86, 778-86 (1966)].	$C_{24}H_{30}O_8$ [I, R = OH; R ₁ = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = H; n = 6].	C, 64.36 H, 6.93	64.57 6.72	[Dioxime m.p. 195° (dil. ethanol) [Found : N, 5.71; $C_{24}H_{32}O_8N_2$ requires N, 5.88%].	Violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Infrared spectrum (KBr Wafer) ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹); 2880, 1640, 1590, 1515, 1266, 1020, 820.
	b) ω-[2-hydroxy, 3,4-dimethoxy benzoyl]-heptanoic acid, m.p. 93° (hot water).	$C_{16}H_{22}O_6$ [II, R = OH; R ₁ = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = H; n = 6].	C, 61.71 H, 6.83	61.93 7.10		

TABLE II—Contd.

Phenols and Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis		Derivatives	Remarks
			Found %	Required %		
7. Veratrole (in tetrachloro ethane).	a) 1,8 bis-[3,4-dimethoxy phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione, m.p. 143° (ethanol)	$C_{24}H_{30}O_6$ [I, R=R ₁ =H; R ₂ =R ₃ =OMe; n = 6].	C, 69.30 H, 7.13	69.56 7.25	2 : 4 D.N.P.H. m.p. 230° (acetic acid) [Found : N, 14.71; C ₃₆ H ₃₈ N ₈ O ₁₂ requires N, 14.47%].	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ yields a product identical with veratric acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 180°. Infrared spectrum (KBr Wafer) ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹): 2857, 1669, 1600, 1587, 1520, 1022, 876, 825.
	b) ω-[3,4-dimethoxy benzoyl]-heptanoic acid, m.p. 85° (hot water).	$C_{16}H_{22}O_5$ [II, R=R ₁ =H; R ₂ =R ₃ =OMe; n = 6].	C, 65.09 H, 6.23	65.31 7.48	2 : 4 D.N.P.H. m.p. 236° (methanol) [Found : N, 11.41; C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₄ requires N, 11.81%].	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
8. 4-Bromo Resorcinol (in nitrobenzene).	a) 1,8 bis-[2,4-dihydroxy, 5-bromo phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione, m.p. 226° (acetic acid).	$C_{20}H_{20}O_6Br_2$ [I, R=R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =H; R ₃ =Br; n = 6].	C, 46.43 H, 4.02	46.51 3.87	Dioxime, m.p. 215° (dil. ethanol) [Found : N, 5.41; C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₂ requires N, 5.12%].	Violet colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Methylation gives a product identical with the bromo resorcinol dimethyl ether and suberyl chloride m.p. 201°.
	b) ω-[2,4-dihydroxy 5-bromobenzoyl]-heptanoic acid, m.p. 161° (dil. ethanol).	$C_{14}H_{17}O_5Br$ [II, R=R ₂ =OH; R ₁ =H; R ₃ =Br; n = 6].	C, 48.42 H, 5.10	48.69 4.93	2 : 4 D.N.P.H. m.p. 174° (methanol) [Found : N, 10.92; C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₂ Br requires N, 10.66%].	Wine red colouration with FeCl ₃ solution.
9. 4-Bromo Resorcinol Dimethyl ether (in nitrobenzene)	1,8 bis-[2,4-dimethoxy, 5-bromo phenyl]-octane 1,8 dione, m.p. 201° (acetic acid).	$C_{24}H_{28}O_6Br_2$ [I, R=R ₂ =OMe; R ₁ =H; R ₃ =Br; n = 6].	C, 50.16 H, 4.99	50.35 4.90	2 : 4 D.N.P.H. m.p. 224° (benzene) [Found : N, 11.82; C ₃₆ H ₃₈ O ₁₂ N ₈ Br ₂ requires N, 12.01%].	No characteristic colouration with FeCl ₃ solution. Oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ gives 5-bromo-β-resorcylic acid dimethyl ether m.p. and mixed m.p. 194°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

1,7 bis-(2,4-dihydroxy phenyl)-heptane 1,7 dione (I, $R = R_2 = OH$; $R_1 = R_3 = H$; $n = 5$):—A solution of freshly distilled resorcinol (5.5 g.) in nitrobenzene (30 ml) was taken in a three-necked flask (250 ml.) equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a dropping funnel and a calcium chloride guard tube. The solution was cooled to 0° and anhydrous aluminium chloride (10 g.) was added to it. Pimelyl chloride (5 g.) diluted with nitrobenzene (10 ml.) was added dropwise from the dropping funnel during a period of one hour. The stirring was continued for a further period of three hours during which the mixture was allowed slowly to attain the room temperature. It was left overnight at this temperature, then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and steam distilled to remove the nitrobenzene. The crude product which solidified on cooling was treated with NaHCO_3 solution when a portion remained insoluble. This was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in needles, m.p. 165° , yield 6 g. (Found : C, 65.98; H, 6.07 $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 66.28; H, 5.81%). The alcoholic solution of the diketone produced a violet colouration with ferric chloride solution.

The bis 2 : 4-D.N.P.H. was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 213° (Found : N, 15.67; $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_{12}\text{N}_8$ requires N, 15.91%).

The structure of the above diketone was confirmed thus : (a) On methylation of the above diketone with dimethyl sulphate and alkali a product was obtained which was identified as 1,7 bis (2,4-dimethoxy phenyl)-heptane 1,7 dione, a diketone which is also obtained from the condensation of resorcinol dimethyl ether and pimelyl chloride. 1,7 bis-(2,4-dimethoxy phenyl)-heptane 1,7 dione on oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate yielded β -resorcylic acid dimethyl ether.

The compounds obtained from other phenols and phenolic ethers, prepared in the same way are described in Table I. The compounds prepared with suberyl chloride are described in Table II.

One of us (M.S.) is grateful to the Governing Body of Annada Mohan Kusum Kumari Scholarship for a scholarship.

Chemical Laboratory,
University College of Science,
Calcutta-9.

Received August 25, 1970